

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-11

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGINEERING GRAPHICS IN IMPROVING THE SKILLS OF FINE ARTS AND ENGINEERING GRAPHICS TEACHERS.

Professor D.E.Omonov, Department of Fine Arts and Engineering Graphics, Faculty of Arts, Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute

Z.Xazratova Engineering Graphics Department of Engineering Graphics and Design Theory 2nd year master

Annotation

According to the qualification description, the teacher of "Fine Art and Drawing" is a highly qualified specialist in folk decorative art, technical creativity, artistic design, leading technical and artistic design circles, as well as decorating schools and classrooms at the required level. is required. To date, it is necessary to creatively improve the content of the educational process in order to form the qualities listed above in the future teachers.

Key words: individual, composition, engineering, computer, communication, monitoring

If we analyze the content and structure of the drawing course taught in the "Fine Art and Engineering Graphics" bachelor's course from the point of view of the specialist's professional activity, we will face a number of shortcomings. Firstly, the pedagogical direction of the materials and the future professional activity of the graduate were not taken into account when describing theoretical and practical information; secondly, most of the individual graphic assignments performed by students have been neglected by the pedagogical direction, thirdly, the content of the graphic core in the qualification recommendation letter of the teacher of fine arts and engineering graphics has not been brought into one system. In our republic, teachers of drawing and painting are mainly trained in "fine arts and engineering graphics" bachelor courses. Sometimes drawing can be taught by teachers of vocational education in general secondary schools. Drawing and painting teachers are assigned the task of conducting training in other subjects of the graphic cycle in vocational colleges based on the specialist qualification. These subjects have their own characteristics according to the direction of specialization. Examples of subjects included in graphic arts in vocational colleges include design, construction drawing, artistic planning, topographical drawing, applied graphics (advertising and industrial graphics), print design, poster, computer graphics, interior and equipment architecture, and graphic design. a set of subjects can be shown.

As a result of the above-mentioned shortcomings, a textbook that fully covers the program materials from drawing has not been published for students of the "Fine Arts and Engineering Graphics" undergraduate course. Most of the existing textbooks do not cover the features of education, in particular, the feature of the future professional activity of a graphic designer-pedagogue. We can fully express this opinion in relation to the independent assignment options given to graphic pedagogues.

Also, if we take into account the artistic education of the "Fine Art and Drawing" teacher, he is an artist-designer in vocational colleges, an artist in industrial design, an artist of industrial equipment and transport systems, an artist of objects of cultural and household importance, We must also emphasize that they can conduct training in many specialties, such as a pattern artist, a lacquer

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-11

miniature artist, a calligraphy and miniature artist, an artist in the fields of decorative applied arts. Teachers of drawing and fine arts can conduct classes of higher methodical level of these subjects. Because they are expected to acquire fundamental and in-depth knowledge, skills and competences during their education in the universities of fine arts, drawing and drawing geometry (along with the perspective section). Designers and art designers need knowledge and skills in these areas. It is necessary to look for ways to include modern subjects in the model curriculum in order to make it possible to pass additional courses in graphic arts in vocational colleges, and to organize facultative and clubs from similar fields in general education schools.

In most of these directions, if students have acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications during their education at a higher educational institution, they can master some new modern subjects through professional development and independent study. possible In that case, it is crucial how the teacher develops the skills of independent work, effective use of educational and scientific-methodological literature. it is of great importance in the formation of qualities such as freedom and hard work. It is impossible to train teachers of "Fine Art and Drawing" according to modern standards without extensive and in-depth teaching of the science of drawing and its branches. It is particularly important for students to know the information about the use of drawing in life, technology, science, architecture, and design. Drawing is objectively considered an independent strong block of specialized sciences. That is why knowledge, skills and competences in drawing and drawing geometry (especially its "Persviktiva" section) are often separated from fine and applied arts in professional activity. is necessary.

With the development of computer graphics, it can be observed that the interest in making high-quality drawings by hand among students began to decrease somewhat. It is difficult to imagine making a competent drawing on a computer without acquiring fundamental knowledge of drawing and good graphic techniques. We believe that it is very useful to include brief information about the history of drawing tools and their current status in developed countries in the textbooks and training manuals of future drawing and painting teachers. This increases students' interest in graphic arts. Most of the textbooks published so far for students of "fine arts and drawing" do not have such a section. The skills of working with dreams and paints using drawing tools and stencils are also useful for the future teacher.

The teacher of "Fine Art and Drawing" must have mastered the basics of graphic design. Unfortunately, the technique of working with dreams and paints is not covered in Uzbek language textbooks and training manuals. It's time to create such guides for students and those interested in decorative arts.

The knowledge of the teacher who teaches drawing should be wide and deep in the field of graphic science, beyond the scope of evaluating students' knowledge. For this, the teacher:

- The history, modern state and prospects of development of graphic arts and their teaching methodology;
- Sections of graphics such as "Numeric projections", "Perspective", "Shadows", "Axonometric projections";

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-11

- It will be useful to know the practical applications of graphics apparatus in science, technology, design, life, creative activities of young people, creative biographies of famous geometers and pedagogues, interesting graphic tasks and games.

In recent years, a number of positive works have been carried out in these directions in our country. In particular, at the Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute, students are taught the history of graphics and creative biographies of scientists who contributed to its development. Work is being carried out to improve the content of graphics cycle subjects in other HEIs. However, it is difficult to say that the changes in the education system of the republic are not fully reflected in the model curriculum. Modern subjects are not included in the cycle of graphics, the features of pedagogical activities are not taken into account in the model curricula of visual arts, drawing geometry, perspective and drawing subjects. On top of that, the time allocated to study drawing geometry and drawing has been reduced in the current model curriculum, and the modules of the subjects have been combined.

It is natural that the expressed opinions will be controversial, and the participants of the conference may have different approaches to the issue. However, it is necessary to pay maximum attention to the methodical development vectors of the graphic education system and the directions of development of the educational system of our society when preparing the next normative documents of the "Fine Art and Drawing" bachelor's course.

Here, let's briefly touch on the requirements for textbooks and training manuals for graphic design subjects:

1. Reflecting social and humanitarian trends:
 - a) Practical benefit in everyday life;
 - b) Information from areas such as aesthetic orientation and universal culture-history, art history, architectural design;
 - c) Positive emotional sensitivity;
 - d) Formation and development of interest in science;
 - e) Development of artistic abilities of students - future teachers of fine arts and drawing;
 - f) Development of personal and creative abilities;
2. Technical and polytechnic direction;
3. General pedagogical direction;
4. Special Caspian lighting and access to the "Fine Art and Drawing" specialist model;
5. Use of new information and pedagogical technologies;
6. The existence of interactions between graphic cycle subjects and other subjects in the curriculum;
7. The existence of mutual relations between the structural parts of the graphic cycle.

Conclusion

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-11

Most of these requirements are interrelated, one logically follows from the other, the existence of one determines the need for the other. If the above students try their best to fulfill each newly created new literature, it will contribute to the increase in the quality and efficiency of education.

REFERENCES:

1. D. E. Omonov, J.T.Kholikov, Sh.X.Egamova., The Role and Importance of Using Graphic Programs in Shaping Students' Knowledge and Skills. Nexus : Journal of Innovative Studies of Engineering Science (JISES) Volume: 01 Issue: 04 | 2022 ISSN: 2751-7578 <http://innosci.org/> 45 | Page
2. D. E. Omonov, S.M.Suvankulov, J.Kh.Kadyrov., The Role of Continents and Neighborhoods in the History of Samarkand Nexus : Journal of Innovative Studies of Engineering Science (JISES) Volume: 01 Issue: 04 | 2022 ISSN: 2751-7578 <http://innosci.org/> 27 | Page
3. D. E. Omonov, S.M.Suvankulov, J.Kh.Kadyrov., Decorations Used in the Interior of Historical Residences of Uzbekistan and Their Situation Today (in the example of the city of Samarkand) Nexus : Journal of Innovative Studies of Engineering Science (JISES) Volume: 01 Issue: 04 | 2022 ISSN: 2751-7578 <http://innosci.org/> 32 | Page
4. I. U. Izbasarov, I.Sh.Suvonkulov, D.E.Omonov., Spatial Imagination and Logical Thinking as a Pedagogical Basis for Teaching Students to Design Nexus : Journal of Innovative Studies of Engineering Science (JISES) Volume: 01 Issue: 04 | 2022 ISSN: 2751-7578 <http://innosci.org/> 37 | Page
5. D. E. Omonov., Conceptual Bases of the Production of Teaching Technologies in Exposure and Practical Training (In the Example of the Engineering Graphics Course) Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress (JARSP) Volume: 01 Issue: 04 | 2022 ISSN: 2751-7551 http://innosci.org 104 | Page
6. D. E. Omonov., The Role of Engineering Graphics in the Training of "Fine Arts and Drawing" Teachers Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress (JARSP) Volume: 01 Issue: 04 | 2022 ISSN: 2751-7551 <http://innosci.org> 108 | Page
7. I. U. Izbosarov, D.E.Omonov, S.Abduvohidova., Stages of Working Thematic Composition in Fine Arts Lessons Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress (JARSP) Volume: 01 Issue: 04 | 2022 ISSN: 2751-7551 <http://innosci.org> 112 | Page
8. D. E. Omonov, M.S.Sidikova, Sh.X.Egamova, F.O.Jahonova., Conceptual bases of production of teaching technologies in lectures and practical classes of engineering graphics international journal of progressive sciences and technologies. (IJPSAT) ISSN: 2509-0119. © 2021 International Journals of Sciences and High Technologies <http://ijpsat.ijsh-t-journals.org> Vol. 29 No. 2 November 2021, pp.84-87
9. D. E. Omonov, M.S.Sidikova, A.I.Temirova, F.G'.Otayorova., Integration Of Computer Technologies In Secondary Schools Of Fine Arts. International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) ISSN: 2509-0119. © 2021 International Journals of Sciences and High Technologies <http://ijpsat.ijsh-t-journals.org> Vol. 29 No. 1 October 2021, pp.497-499
10. DILSHOD ESONOVICH OMONOV., Ways to introduce the science of painting to the visual arts using new pedagogical technologies. International journal of philosophical studies and Social sciences ISSN-E: 2181-2047, ISSN-P: 2181-2039 <http://ijpsss.iscience.uz/index.php/ijpsss> Vol 1, Issue 3 2021

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-11

11. D. E. Omonov., Integration of fine arts and computer technologies in art education of students. MIDDLE EUROPEAN SCIENTIFIC BULLETIN ISSN 2694-9970 Middle European Scientific Bulletin, VOLUME 17 Oct 2021
12. Copyright (c) 2021 Author (s). This is an open -access article distributed under the terms of Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY).To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
13. Omonov Dilshod Esonovich., Spiritual values and their importance in human development. NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN ENGINEERING RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY [IJIERT] ISSN : 2394-3696 Website: ijiert.org VOLUME 8, ISSUE 10, Oct. -2021 199 | P a g e
14. D. E. Omonov., Improving Conversation Classes on Fine Arts in Secondary Schools. European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education (EJINE) Volume 2 | Issue 2 | ISSN: 2795-8612.
15. D.E.Omonov., the Role of Graphics in the Training of Teachers of "Fine Arts and Engineering Graphics" European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education (EJINE) Volume 2 | Issue 2 | ISSN: 2795-8612.
16. D. E. Omonov, G. Namozova, F. Rashidov, S. Abduvohidova., Engineering graphic sciences are a conceptual framework for conducting educational technologies in lectures and practical training.